

THE ROLE OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN PROMOTING LEGAL CULTURE IN SOCIETY: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND PRACTICE

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Annotation: The article compares some aspects of the legal system of foreign countries and the activities of the internal affairs bodies (police) and the theoretical and legal bases for raising the legal culture in the society. In addition, the tasks and functions of some law enforcement agencies in foreign countries, including the internal affairs bodies, the state of interaction with the public in their activities, the problems encountered and the factors affecting it, and the views of scientists on the topic and legislative documents were studied to improve the legal culture of citizens. Improvement of the activities of the internal affairs bodies related to raising the legal culture in the society as a result of the study of foreign experience, the issues of implementation into the national legislation, and future tasks were discussed in detail.

Keywords. law, rule of law, legal consciousness, legal culture, police, public organization, civil society, legal information, legal propaganda, legal education, regulatory legal document, local government, internal affairs bodies.

In recent years, the principle of "state-society-individual" is being replaced by the principle of "person-society-state" under the reforms implemented in recent years. This idea is reflected in the adopted legislative documents. Of course, one of the main tasks of today is to accurately communicate the positive results of such reforms and future goals and strategies to citizens. At this point, the issue of raising the legal culture in society by increasing the legal literacy of the population and establishing a sense of obedience to the law in the citizens is still relevant.

This requires the development of modern methods and approaches to improve the legal culture of society and the study of foreign experience.

During the research, we will focus on the experiences of countries with different legal systems and where legal culture is highly developed and developing in society.

It is known that the United Arab Emirates, which has its position in the Middle East, but also in the world, is known for its strictest laws in the world and a strong judicial system. The judicial system in this country is based on the Muslim legal system. Although the citizens of the country are less than 10 million, and almost all of them are Muslims, if we take into account that on average 16-17 million tourists visit this country per year, at first glance, the idea arises that it would be better to take a model from secular legal systems in the country. However, it should not be forgotten that the legal system established in the country and its norms should serve the interests of the local population. Tourists visiting the country are forced to comply with the established laws whether they want to or not. Despite the strict laws and sanctions for violating them, the number of tourists entering the Emirates, especially its central cities, is increasing year by year. So what is so special about this legal system? Why do the same legal norms apply to millions of residents and tourists throughout the country, but no conflicts arise? It can be seen that the main reason for this is the sanctions. Heavy fines and punishments, even for simple infractions, are certainly a force to compel everyone to obey the law.

For example, in the United Arab Emirates, there are such norms of dress code that you can even go to jail for violating them. Even the types of clothing are specified in such norms. In addition, in this country, even social networks are controlled, and insulting and using inappropriate words can be the basis for a fine of up to 1000 US dollars. In addition, the relations of citizens in general for all individuals are regulated to such an ordinary domestic level that among them even asking for a woman's hand or holding hands in a public place is forbidden, and there are very severe penalties for violating them. Also, there are such restrictions on taking pictures, eating in public, behaving, and driving, that even citizens are afraid to violate them. If it is assumed, what kind of punishments can be prescribed for crimes such as assassination, theft, corruption, defamation, and treason in a country that has established such punishments for the simplest crimes? Religious norms were taken as a basis for the development of the legal system established in the state. This is also reflected in the motto of the country. "Allah, the people, and the president." This is the national motto of the United Arab Emirates¹.

It can be seen that the laws of the country as mentioned above are mandatory for everyone, including millions of foreign tourists who visit each year. After all, as the Prime Minister of the country, Anwar Gargash, said, "Developing special norms for visitors to our country and creating special conditions for them means trampling our holy religion." While tourists obey the laws only because of the harsh sanctions, the citizens of the country obey these norms from the point of view of ethics. Because of this, almost none of the citizens break the law. Offenders are mostly tourists. But as a result of the strictly established laws and law enforcement agencies, the country is one of the safest regions in the world. In particular, the level of safety in it is 81.9% in 2018 and 84.5% in 2019, and it is among the safest countries in the world after countries such as Singapore, Malaysia, and Qatar².

In addition, the rate of committing serious crimes in the country is 0.8%, which means the 19th place in the world. The main key to these results, as mentioned above, is primarily heavy sanctions. This experience has been applied by some countries in history, and it certainly gave its positive results. For example, in the laws of Hammurabi, and the laws of Dracont, during the legislative period of the emir Nasrullah, the crime and crime among the population decreased to such an extent that there are even historical sources about the emptying of the prisons. Second, long-term heavy prison sentences for law enforcement officials and judges for abuse of office or profession. Through this, it is possible to force them to approach their profession professionally. The right thing goes back to the sanctions, but it is precisely through this that the mechanism of their activity is created, which works like clockwork. The main principles of their activity include an intolerant attitude against any crime, immediate elimination of any violation, and unconditional provision of the primacy of the law. At first glance, such an arrangement seems like the old feudal law or a violation of human rights. In particular, in one of the articles of the "Novate" publishing house, "There are no elements of democracy in the

¹ "The safest countries"-WHO: "Global Health Estimates"-2019.

² С.О.Усмонов, А.А.Мирзарахмонов. 2021. Qonunchilik va sud-huquq tizimini rivojlantirishda jahon davlatlari tajribalari va ularni O'zbekistonda tadbiq etish istiqbollari. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 December 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 12. – Б.574-582.

country, all laws are based on coercion and torture." It is not possible to achieve any results in today's society without this³.

But it is these laws that appear in the Arab Emirates as a unique solution to public order and crime prevention. At this point, it would be appropriate to learn about sanctions from this legal system. Of course, it is clear that the application of severe sanctions for crimes of high social risk, but not for all areas, will drastically reduce the number of these crimes.

Alternatively, warning signs in the form of traffic signs have been installed or posted in cities and residential areas of the country for ordinary citizens and tourists to see. Prohibited behavior and types of offenses leading to administrative or criminal liability are illustrated in these signs. A citizen or tourist who sees this sign stops performing the action indicated in it or does not do it at all.

UAE law prohibits photography of military installations, government facilities and buildings, and private property. Local women should not be photographed and permission must be sought if one wishes to take a memorable photo with the local population. For serious offences, strict UAE laws can carry both fines and imprisonment. As a rule, they rarely try to punish tourists in this country, but violation of the current legislation can lead to a ban on entry into the country for tourists and the denial of a visa in the future. At the same time, in case of minor violations due to ignorance of local laws, tourists, as a rule, are first politely warned about the violation, and if the offender deliberately and grossly disregards the rules, appropriate measures can be taken by the authorities. Police officers are rarely seen on the street, but when there is an emergency, a crime, they immediately arrive at the scene⁴.

It is known that in recent years in our country, legislative documents on increasing the legal literacy of citizens and liberalization of criminal punishments have been adopted. Of course, the main goal of these cases is the reliable protection of human rights and freedoms, and legal interests. However, the other side of the issue is that one person's illegal behavior leads to the violation of the rights and interests of another person or persons. This requires the establishment of a procedure imposing equal rights and obligations on both sides of the legislation.

The establishment of severe sanctions for crimes can completely change the mind of a person who intends to commit an offense. For example, a person who wants to commit suicide will certainly refrain from doing so if he thinks that he will be punished for it. This type of punishment is used in the USA, China, Iran, and most Arab countries of the world. And of course, the types of crimes that are threatened with this sanction are very different compared to other countries. Widespread application of sanctions such as large fines, confiscation of property for non-payment of fines, long prison terms, and even the death penalty for high-risk crimes can lead to a reduction in these types of crimes.

In this case, attention should be focused not on the application of this punishment, but on encouraging people not to commit crimes by the threat of this punishment. An example of this

³ С.О.Усмонов, А.А.Мирзарахмонов. 2021. Qonunchilik va sud-huquq tizimini rivojlantirishda jahon davlatlari tajribalari va ularni O'zbekistonda tadbiq etish istiqbollari. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 December 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 12. – Б.574-582.

⁴ РФ Интернет портали маълумотларидан олинди: www/russian-dubai.com/news-blog/life-in-uae/184-zakony-dubaya-uae. Мурожаат санаси 16.03.2023й

is that tourists in the United Arab Emirates reluctantly obey the laws of the Muslim legal system because they are afraid of punishment.

Based on the experience of the UAE, it can be concluded that learning and adopting the experience of imposing punishments and warning signs in this country can help in increasing the literacy of the population of the country and forming a sense of obedience to the law.

The next object of our research is the Federal Republic of Germany, where the legal culture of the society in the European region is provided at a high level. Germany is famous for its law-abiding behavior and strong discipline of the German people. Germany has strict laws.

The legal system established in Germany is based on the "Roman-Germanic" legal system, which has been developed since ancient times. For German citizens, the court is a special body, it is the real defender of the rights and interests of citizens and the original embodiment of justice. Many scholars attribute this to the mentality of the German people, while some explain that the German judicial system was inherited from the Roman Empire, which was the seat of jurisdiction.

German laws cover almost all aspects of life, and we will look at some of them. First of all, in Germany, there is such an attitude towards law enforcement agencies and military personnel that interference in their legal activities, personal interests, and personality by citizens is strictly prohibited and severely punished.

For example, a citizen who addresses a police officer as "Du" meaning "you" will be fined 600 euros. Officers are only required to be addressed as "Sie" ie "you". There is a list of words and gestures, gestures, and hand movements that are punishable by such citizens when they communicate with a police officer, and separate fine amounts are set for each situation. Including "Dumme kuh" (Stupid cow) 300-600 euros, "Du blodes Schwein" (pig) 500 euros, "Du Wichser" (your mother) 1000 euros, Raubritter (robber baron) 1500 euros, "Mittelfinger zeigen" (middle finger pointing) a fine of 600-4000 euros is applied⁵. Through such simple laws, respect for law enforcement officers was formed among citizens, not voluntarily, but compulsorily. It is this aspect that is unique. It is very important to maintain a certain boundary between citizens and civil servants and build this boundary based on mutual respect. As the German politician Horst Zeehofer noted: "The attitude of citizens to public servants is always an important issue." In a situation where it is difficult to achieve respect consciously, it is appropriate to take a coercive measure. The German people are considered by everyone to be orderly people who do everything in an orderly manner. It is even legalized, in particular, every office should have a window with a view of the sky, or we can cite examples such as the "Day of Peace" law⁶.

"Day of Silence" is a nationwide law that bans noise, celebrations, and the use of any loud equipment on the day of rest, and the purpose of this law is to ensure that citizens spend the day off in a meaningful and undisturbed manner. Because meaningful entertainment increases the efficiency of work. What we mean to say is that all the habits of order and discipline of the German people as we know them are codified, and heavy fines and even worse punishments are prescribed for breaking them. It is this aspect that can be mastered, that is, the relations

⁵ Интернет материалларидан олинди. www.ltv.ru/news/2012-06-08/94288-v_germanii_shtraf_v_600_evro_mozhnopoluchit_uzhe_za_to_chno_obratilsya_k_politseyskomu_na_ty

⁶ А. Uspeshnaya. "Необычные законы ФРГ"-«Germania One»-2020

that we believe should be regulated based on moral norms should also be regulated by law. Because leaving obedience to the law to the will of citizens does not always bear fruit. A right comes into action only when it is legalized and demanded based on specific norms.

Meanwhile, in 2014, thanks to the "open door" policy put forward by Angela Merkel, millions of immigrants from the south began to move to the federal territories of Germany. This policy unexpectedly began to backfire. Until 2018, the crime rate in the country has been steadily increasing, and the number of offenses recorded this year was 5.76 million, and in 2019, this figure dropped to 5.4 million, and 30% of them were criminally punished. It should be noted that most of the crimes are committed by migrants. So how did the government manage to reduce these crimes? The main motive here was from the German people themselves, who, under the "open door" policy, began to punish law-breaking offenders by immigrating. Efforts to brutally punish migrants who have committed crimes such as theft, defamation, and invasion have intensified. This explains the high level of indicators after this policy. Over time, migrants realized that if they wanted to live in Germany, they had to obey the law without question. The policies of the government, such as the expansion of the police force, the granting of broad powers to the police, and the issuance of personal numbers for immigrants, have not been effective⁷.

What matters here is the national consciousness and mentality of the German people, because they not only obey the laws, but they can also force others to obey the laws. In the words of Grotius, "Any legal system is successful if the obedience to the laws is carried out based on the will of the citizens." And in raising it to the level of desire, it turns out that the German experience is unique and effective.

If we can instill in the minds of young people in our country the same respect for laws as in Germany, the future generation will be able to become citizens of a highly developed country. In conclusion, we can state that each country's legal system has its shortcomings and achievements. Based on these, we would make the following suggestions. Experiences from the United Arab Emirates in strengthening sanctions for violations, developing a unique mechanism for the timely delivery of newly adopted laws to the population, further clarifying the legal attitudes protected or prohibited in the adoption of laws, and from the Federal Republic of Germany a unique privilege for judges and people's advisers in the judicial system. and experiences in the issue of demands, experiences in creating a more complex network of courts and their specialization, the mechanism of regulating relations between law enforcement officers and citizens, as well as examples of laws about alcohol and "day of peace", the scope of relations regulated by law it is necessary to consider the issues of mastering the experience of expansion and, most importantly, the experience of developing a consistent mechanism of instilling respect for laws into the minds and consciousness of the population. When introducing these experiences into the national legal system, it is necessary to approach them based on the level of development of the country and the mentality of the people (not blindly, of course). In addition, in the countries analyzed above, these legal systems have made it possible to achieve great progress in crime prevention. Because in achieving these results,

⁷ С.О.Усмонов, А.А.Мирзарахмонов. 2021. Qonunchilik va sud-huquq tizimini rivojlantirishda jahon davlatlari tajribalari va ularni O'zbekistonda tadbiq etish istiqbollari. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal / ISSN 2181-0842 December 2021 / Volume 2 Issue 12. – Б.574-582.

the legal system established in the country, the institution of justice, the practical expression of the rule of law, and, of course, the effective activity of law enforcement agencies play a big role. The main goal of studying foreign experiences and organizing the prospects of their implementation in the country is to apply them in practice, taking a model from the judicial system of the developed countries of the world, and as a result, to establish a legal democratic state.

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